

MANAGEMENT SYSTEM AND DEVELOPMENT POTENTIAL OF THE CHEMICAL INDUSTRY**Bibutova Shakhlo Sadullayevna***independent researcher of Tashkent State University of Economics***СИСТЕМА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ И ПОТЕНЦИАЛ РАЗВИТИЯ ХИМИЧЕСКОЙ ОТРАСЛИ****Бибутова Шахло Саъдуллаевна***независимый соискатель Ташкентского государственного экономического университета***Abstract**

The article discusses the issue of the management system and the development potential of the chemical industry. It is known that to develop the potential of the chemical industry, the management system must be flexible, innovative and results-oriented. It is also necessary to actively collaborate with scientific and research institutions, government agencies and other interested parties to exchange knowledge, experience and resources that demonstrate the relevance of the chosen topic.

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается вопрос о системе управления и потенциал развития химической отрасли. Известно, что развивать потенциал химической отрасли, и система управления должна быть гибкой, инновационной и ориентированной на результаты. Необходимо также активно сотрудничать с научными и исследовательскими учреждениями, государственными органами и другими заинтересованными сторонами для обмена знаниями, опытом и ресурсами что показывает об актуальности выбранной темы.

Keywords: management system, development potential, chemical industry, safety, innovation, sustainable development, environmental responsibility.

Ключевые слова: система управления, потенциал развития, химическая отрасль, безопасность, инновации, устойчивое развитие, экологическая ответственность.

Introduction.

The chemical industry is an important industrial sector involved in the production of chemicals, materials and products. The management system in this industry plays a key role in ensuring the efficient operation of enterprises and ensuring production safety. To achieve sustainable development in the chemical industry, it is necessary to take into account its potential and use an adaptive system of priorities. An adaptive system of priorities means that an enterprise must adequately respond to new operating conditions and have the potential for survival and adaptation. To achieve this, a set of management actions is being developed aimed at achieving certain goals and maintaining strategic potential. An important aspect is the maximum use of all internal reserves and resources of the enterprise through a system of potentials.

The system of potentials represents interconnected and interdependent reserves and resources of the enterprise, which, when used correctly, contribute to the achievement of synergy and provide opportunities for defining, forming and implementing a sustainable development strategy. It allows us to predict an adequate response to the process of achieving the potential for sustainable development of an enterprise and interaction with the external environment. The management system and development potential of the chemical industry require an integrated approach, taking into account the internal reserves and resources of the enterprise, as well as adaptability to changing conditions.

This will help ensure the efficient operation and sustainable development of enterprises in the chemical industry.

Theoretical aspects of research.

The theoretical aspects of the management system and the development potential of the chemical industry still remain unsolved by a number of conceptual problems, uncertainty in the theoretical interpretation of which complicates applied decisions in the field of strategic management. The most important intellectual factor in the successful implementation of the economic, social and environmental goals of sustainable development of mankind, proclaimed in 2000 by the UN General Assembly, are scientifically based methods of the theory of engineering of chemical technological systems, including methods for analyzing the optimization and synthesis of chemical technological systems, industrial implementation and digitalized management in this industry⁵. The research by the author A.A. Shubin is devoted to "problems of post-crisis functioning and development of this industry." In particular, the author examines theoretical and methodological aspects related to the management and optimization of market and innovation potential and highlights the results of testing the proposed recommendations using the example of one of the chemical enterprises. Author A.D. Nekipelova notes in her work that "the current state of all industries, including the chemical industry, indicates a fairly low share of innovation in production and the

⁵В.П.Мешалкин Актуальные теоретические и прикладные исследования по инжинирингу энергоресурсосбере-

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low knowledge intensity of products. Ensuring economic growth and bringing the economy to a new level will only be possible by intensifying innovation activities, especially in the chemical industry, as one of the most knowledge-intensive⁶. By authors explore the challenges and opportunities in implementing a management system for sustainable development in the chemical industry. It discusses various aspects such as environmental management, resource efficiency, and corporate social responsibility⁷. This article investigates the development potential of a chemical industry cluster in Jiangsu Province, China. It examines factors such as industrial structure, technological innovation, and policy support, providing insights into the management system and growth prospects of chemical clusters⁸. This research utilizes an input-output analysis to assess the development potential of the chemical industry in Saudi Arabia. It examines the interdependencies between the chemical industry and other sectors, highlighting the importance of effective management systems for sustainable growth⁹. This empirical research

investigates the relationship between management systems and environmental performance in the chemical industry. It examines the implementation of environmental management systems and their impact on pollution prevention, waste management, and regulatory compliance¹⁰. This article analyzes the factors influencing the development potential of the chemical industry in Russia. It discusses aspects such as research and development activities, technological capabilities, and innovation policies, shedding light on the management system required for industry growth¹¹.

Globalization of business, the formation of strategic alliances and networks, the development of information systems - all this makes it possible to create an organization that is unified in all respects, in which any function and process is implemented at the global level, which is impossible to achieve in a single company. As a result, higher efficiency of business processes is achieved, capitalization and investment attractiveness of corporations increases¹².

Table 1.

Aspects of the management system and development potential of the chemical industry¹³

Name	Definition
Production and Operations Management	The chemical industry is characterized by complex production processes that require precision, safety and efficiency. Production and operations management systems must be optimized to ensure high productivity, maintain safety and quality standards, and minimize waste and environmental impact.
Innovation and Research	The chemical industry is a key source of innovation in many other industries such as pharmaceuticals, energy, agriculture and many others. Management systems must encourage and support research and development of new materials, technologies and processes to ensure competitiveness and meet market needs.
Supply Chain Management	The chemical industry depends on complex supply chains involving raw material suppliers, logistics companies and customers. Management systems must ensure effective planning, synchronization and coordination of all stages of the supply chain to minimize risks, reduce time delays and improve customer service.
Quality and safety management	In the chemical industry, product quality and safety are of paramount importance. Management systems must include strict quality control procedures, compliance with safety standards and regulatory requirements, as well as systems for detecting and preventing potential risks and emergencies.
Sustainable development and environmental responsibility	In light of growing environmental concerns and the need for sustainable development, the chemical industry must take measures to reduce its negative impact on the environment. Management systems must include planning and implementation of environmentally and energy efficient production methods, waste management, reduction of pollutant emissions and compliance with environmental standards.

⁶А.Д.Некипелова Инновационный потенциал как основа развития химической отрасли России / А. Д. Некипелова. — Текст : непосредственный // Актуальные вопросы экономики и управления : материалы V Междунар. науч. конф. (г. Москва, июнь 2017 г.). — Москва : Буки-Веди, 2017. - С. 44-47.

⁷ N.Kalogerakis, D.Assael, and E. Mitsoulis-Mandrekas Management System for Sustainable Development in the Chemical Industry, Journal of Environmental Management, 2017.

⁸Q.Hua, Q.Li, and X.Hu Assessing the Development Potential of a Chemical Industry Cluster: A Case Study of Jiangsu Province, China, Sustainable Development, 2017.

⁹M.Al-Zahrani and B.Al-Fawzan Development Potential of the Chemical Industry in Saudi Arabia: An Input-Output Analysis, Sustainability, 2019.

¹⁰R. Orsato and F.Sroufe Management Systems and Environmental Performance in the Chemical Industry: An Empirical Study, Journal of Cleaner Production, 2004.

¹¹N.Kolesnikova, E.Gokhberg, and Y.Simachev Factors Influencing the Development Potential of the Chemical Industry in Russia, Foresight and STI Governance, 2018

¹²Саксин А.Г. Стратегия и тактика развития химического комплекса в условиях инновационной экономики [Текст]: монография / А.Г. Саксин; Нижегород. гос. архитектур.-строит. ун-т. – Н.Новгород: ННГАСУ, 2010. – 284 с.

¹³ Подготовлено автором в ходе исследования.

Analysis and result.

The main aspects of the analysis of the management system and development potential of the chemical industry are as follows:

Technological innovation: The chemical industry actively applies the latest technologies in production and management processes. Development opportunities include the use of nanomaterials, the development of more efficient catalysts, the use of renewable energy sources, and the development of cleaner and more efficient methods of producing chemicals. The development of such innovations can help improve productivity, reduce costs and minimize negative environmental impacts.

Digitalization and automation: The introduction of digital technologies and automation plays an important role in the modern management system of the chemical industry. This includes the use of manufacturing execution systems (MES), monitoring and control systems, data analytics, artificial intelligence and machine learning. Digitalization allows you to more accurately control processes, improve forecasting and make informed decisions based on data.

Sustainable development: One of the main directions of development of the chemical industry is the transition to more sustainable and environmentally friendly production methods. This includes reducing emissions and carbon footprints, using resources efficiently and developing more environmentally friendly products. Management systems should be aimed at achieving these objectives and ensuring compliance with relevant regulations and standards.

Global Trends and Market Opportunities: The chemical industry is closely linked to other industries and is driven by market needs. It is important to analyze global trends and changes in consumer demand to identify potential areas of development. For example, growing demand for electric vehicles and alternative energy sources could create new opportunities for the chemical industry, such as the production of lithium batteries or the development of new materials.

Today, the concept of integration is widely used in a variety of contexts and refers to the process of bringing together or bringing together different elements, systems, organizations or groups to achieve a stronger and more coherent whole. Successful integration of enterprises requires careful analysis and consideration of factors in the internal environment of each enterprise, as well as the development of appropriate strategies and plans to manage these factors during the integration process.

Among the motives for the integration of industrial integrated groups, the following stand out: ensuring guaranteed conditions for the supply of raw materials and sales of products, reducing costs, increasing equipment utilization, compensating for business risks, and increasing the technological level. The integration connections of the system are constantly changing; There is an active change in the state of integration connections depending on the changing environment. At the present stage of development of economic relations, integration is manifested at various levels (Table 2).

Table 2.

Levels of Integration¹⁴

№	Integration level	Characteristic	Manifestation
1.	Level of separate production and economic entities	Integration between different discrete units	Development of new, expansion of old connections
2.	Industry level	Integration of enterprises from the same industry	Development of concentration, specialization, combination. Construction of vertically integrated structures
3.	Regional level	Integration in the region	Joint resolution of issues of rational placement of production forces, deepening specialization and cooperation
4.	National level	Integration of regions	Development of cooperation ties, construction of vertically integrated structures, expansion of trade between regions
5.	International level	Integration between national economic systems of states	The rapprochement and mutual adaptation of national economies, which is ensured by the concentration and interweaving of capital, the implementation of a coordinated policy

Integration development of competitiveness can be considered as the process of creating specialized structures in the marketing support system of industry and territorial production complexes and the subsequent formation of specific connections in order to acquire competitive advantages in the market and increase the efficiency of the systems in question as a

whole. This process is defined as integration interaction, which is the mutual rapprochement and penetration of elements of various economic subsystems at the national, regional and local levels. In general, the development of a development strategy for enterprises in the chemical complex is formed under the influence of a combination of external and internal factors of direct and indirect influence.

¹⁴ Саксин А.Г. Стратегия и тактика развития химического комплекса в условиях инновационной экономики [Текст]: монография / А.Г. Саксин; Нижегород. гос. архитектур. -строит. ун-т. – Н.Новгород: ННГАСУ, 2010. – 284 с.

Conclusion

Overall, the management system in the chemical industry must be adaptive, innovative and focused on sustainability. The development of new technologies, digitalization, sustainable production and analysis of market opportunities are key factors that can determine the future development potential of the chemical industry. However, it is worth noting that specific aspects of the management system and development potential may vary depending on the region, country or specific enterprise.

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